

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

PARAMETRIC MODIFICATIONS OF ONE-SAMPLE T-TEST: PART I - SYMMETRIC POPULATIONS

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Abstract

In the current article, a modification of the popular one-sample t-test is proposed. The offered modification of the test uses a C_2 statistic and its standard error. For the sake of comparing the statistical power of the presented variant of the test with the statistical power of the traditional one, some t-tests at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ were performed using random samples of various sizes ($n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50$), which were generated from several symmetric distributions with different properties. The results show that the one-sample t-test based on the C_2 statistic is more powerful and efficient than the traditional one.

Keywords: one-sample t-test; symmetric populations; statistical power; systematic error in precise levelling

Introduction

The conventional one-sample t-test is based on the mean of a sample and the standard error of the mean. It is a well-known fact that the sample mean and its standard error are calculated by equal weighting of all observations in the analyzed sample. As a result, the observations in the tails are overvalued on the back of those observations, which are located near the sample median. Such an approach leads to inflation of the sample variance and the standard error of the sample mean. An additional effect of equal weighting is moving the mean forward to the outliers and contaminated observations

or to the heavy-tailed part in the case of skewed distributions. Because of these facts, the traditional one-sample t-test sometimes produces ambiguous and incorrect test results.

Suppose we have the standardised closing errors in the levelling sections of a levelling line, presented by the sample below.

0.667, -0.020, 0.588, 0.326, 0.415, -0.380, 0.297, -0.392, 0.709, 0.055, 0.226, -0.137

The distribution of the data is illustrated by the histogram in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Histogram of the sample data

According to the assumptions about the distribution of errors in geodesy, these closing errors are normally distributed with an expectation equal to zero. So, we want to test whether or not the mean of our sample is equal to 0 at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. The alternative hypothesis is that the sample mean is different from zero. Thus, we form our null hypothesis $H_0: \mu = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis $H_1: \mu \neq 0$. One can calculate that the sample mean $\bar{X} = 0.1962$ and its standard error $\sigma_{\bar{X}} = \sigma/\sqrt{n} = 0.1090$. The 2-sided t-test statistic $t(0.05, 11, \text{two-tail}) = 2.201$ is greater than $T = 0.1962 / 0.1090 = 1.799$, which is the observed value, given by equation (1).

$$T = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\sigma/\sqrt{n}} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the standard 2-sided one-sample t-test did not reject the null hypothesis. The p-value produced by the 2-sided test is 0.0995.

Let us perform a 1-sided one-sample t-test, where our null hypothesis is $H_0: \mu = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis $H_1: \mu > 0$. This time the 1-sided t-test statistic $t(0.05, 11, \text{one-tail}) = 1.7959 < 1.799 = T = 0.1962 / 0.1090$. The p-value produced by the 1-sided test is $0.0497 < 0.05 = \alpha$. Thus, the 1-sided one-sample t-test is on the edge of accepting the null hypothesis. However, it is not a good idea for the 1-sided tests to be used as a mode to achieve significance. So, could be one sure whether or not the mean of our sample is equal to 0 at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$?

To minimize such ambiguous results as the above example results, we can redefine the t-test statistic (1) in (2) under $H_0: \mu = \mu_0$.

$$T_{c_2} = \frac{\check{X} - \mu}{\sigma_{\check{X}}} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2) the \check{X} denotes a C_2 statistic. The notation $\sigma_{\check{X}}$ means the standard error of the C_2 statistic for given sample data. One can find how the C_2 statistic can be calculated in the study (Cvetkov 2022). The proof, that the above statistic is unbiased and more effective than the mean, is given in (Cvetkov 2023a), where is also shown that (2) is a pivotal quantity and converges to a normal distribution. The better properties of the C_2 statistic in comparison to the mean are the reasons for the greater statistical power of the C_2 -based variant of z-Tests (Cvetkov 2023b). The main objective of the current article is to demonstrate that the conclusions, which were made in (Cvetkov 2023b) regarding samples, which contain more than 50 observations, are also valid in the case of the one-sample t-tests. The results shown below are based on simulations of random samples, derived from symmetric populations.

Simulations

For the sake of comparing the statistical power of the one-sample t-test based on the C_2 statistic with the statistical power of the traditional one-sample t-test, two-sided and one-sided t-tests at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ were performed. In these tests, random samples of various sizes ($n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45,$

50) from some symmetric distributions with different properties were generated and used. These distributions are:

- The standard normal distribution - $N(0,1)$;
- The uniform distribution with parameters set to 0 and 1 - $U(0,1)$;
- Contaminated normal distributions with contamination parameters $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.2$ and scale multiplier $\lambda = 3$ - $CN(0.9, 3)$ and $CN(0.8, 3)$;
- The Laplace distribution with location 0 and scale 1 - $Lp(0, 1)$;
- Heavy-tailed the t-distribution with 4 degrees of freedom - $t(4)$
- Symmetric, bimodal and heavy-tailed distribution such as the Beta distribution with the two parameters set to 0.5 - $B(0.5,0.5)$;
- Symmetric and lighter-tailed distributions such as the Beta distribution with the two parameters set to 2 - $B(2,2)$.

For each given sample size, 10000 replicates were done from each of the above distributions. The null hypothesis of the 2-sided tests is $\mu = \mu_0 + \delta$ and its alternative hypothesis is $\mu \neq \mu_0 + \delta$, where μ_0 is set at the population's true mean and $\delta = \sigma/2$ (σ is the standard deviation of the parent population). Thus, the difference between the hypothesized mean and the population's true mean is δ , so the correct decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Respectively, the null hypothesis of the 1-sided tests is $\mu = \mu_0 + \delta$ and its alternative hypothesis is $\mu < \mu_0 + \delta$.

The number of times which each of the tests commits the type II error, i.e., the null hypothesis was rejected, is counted for each initial sample size ($n = 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50$) and each above listed skewed distributions. These numbers are presented in Figure 2 regarding 2-sided tests and in Figure 3 concerning 1-sided tests, respectively.

Results

Analyzing Figure 2 and Figure 3 is obvious that:

- The statistical power of the C_2 -based modification of the one-sample t-test is greater than that of the mean-based conventional test. This conclusion is valid for all analyzed symmetric distributions if the sample size is below 30 observations.
- When the parent distribution is similar to the $N(0, 1)$, $Lp(0, 1)$, $t(4)$, $CN(0.9, 3)$, $CN(0.8, 3)$ or the $Beta(2, 2)$, the statistical power of the C_2 based modification the one-sample t-test is greater than that of the mean based conventional test.
- When the parent distribution of the analyzed data is symmetric and moderate or heavy-tailed distributions, e.g., the $Beta(0.5, 0.5)$ and the $U(0, 1)$, the power of the mean-based test is equal or even slightly higher than the power of the C_2 test modification if the size of the sample is greater than 30 observations.
- The above conclusions are valid regardless of the definition of the alternative hypothesis, i.e., does not matter the applied sides of the test.

Figure 2: Statistical power of 2-sided One-Sample t-test based on simulations of random samples generated from some symmetric populations.

Figure 3: Statistical power of 1-sided One-Sample t-test based on simulations of random samples generated from some symmetric populations.

The approximate number of observations necessary for the mean-based one-sample t-test to achieve the power of the C_2-based test variant at significance level $\alpha=0.05$ regarding above mentioned symmetric distributions are given in Table 1.

Table 1

The approximate number of observations necessary to the mean-based one-sample t-test to achieve the power of the C₂-based variant of the test at significance level $\alpha=0.05$ and sample size (n=10, 20, 30) for some distributions

Distribution	2-sided			1-sided		
	10	20	30	10	20	30
N(0, 1)	20	30	43	18	26	40
CN(0.9, 3)	20	38	*	20	37	*
CN(0.8, 3)	25	42	*	22	40	*
U(0, 1)	18	27	35	16	24	33
t(4)	22	41	*	20	39	*
Lp(0,1)	24	40	*	24	32	*
Beta(0.5,0.5)	18	26	33	16	24	31
Beta(2,2)	19	29	40	17	26	35

Note: The symbol * denotes more than 50 observations.

According to Table 1, one can see that:

- In the case of the N(0, 1) Beta(2, 2) distribution, the variant of the test, based on the sample mean, needs approximately 1.5 more observations to achieve the power of the C₂-based modification.

- When the parent distribution is contaminated or long-tailed, e.g., CN(0.9, 3), CN(0.8, 3), Lp(0, 1), t(4) the ratio between the mean-based test and C₂-based one is even greater than 1.5.

- Contrary, when the parent distribution of the analyzed data is symmetric and moderate or heavy-tailed distributions, e.g., the Beta(0.5, 0.5) and the U(0, 1), the mean based test needs approximately 1.2 more observations than the C₂ based variant to predefined power to be achieved, if the sample size is up to 20 observations. If the sample size is more than 30 observations, both variants give similar results.

Introduction Example Results

Table 2 presents the results, produced by the mean-based one-sample t-test and the C₂-based test modification with the data sample, given in the Introduction. According to them, the null hypothesis $H_0: \mu = 0$ was rejected by both the 2-sided and 1-sided C₂-based variants at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. The p-values, produced by these tests are 0.022 and 0.011 for 2-sided and 1-sided modes, respectively. In addition, the statistical power of the C₂-based tests is almost 30% higher than that of the mean-based t-tests. Using C₂-based one-sample t-tests, one can be sure that the mean of the analyzed sample differs from 0 at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, because the C₂ statistic and the mean of samples, which derived from symmetric distributions, are theoretically equal.

Table 2

One-Sample t-Test Results				
	Mean	C ₂	Mean	C ₂
1	2	3	4	5
Hypothesis H_0	$\mu = 0$		$\mu = 0$	
Against H_1	$\mu \neq 0$		$\mu > 0$	
Sample Central Statistic	0.1962	0.2176	0.1962	0.2176
Standard Deviation	0.3777	0.2821	0.3777	0.2821
Standard Error	0.1090	0.0814	0.1090	0.0814
Tails	2		1	
Alpha	0.05		0.05	
Sample Size	12		12	
df	11		11	
t-Crit	2.2010		1.7959	
t-Observed	1.7990	2.6722	1.7990	2.6722
p-value	0.0995	0.0217	0.0497	0.0109
Power	0.3487	0.6769	0.5012	0.8002
Significance	no	yes	yes	yes

Conclusions

In this paper, a modification of the one-sample t-test was proposed. This variant of the test uses a C₂ statistic, which is a more efficient estimator of the central tendency than the mean and less sensitive to the effect of outliers, contaminated data and those observations, which are located in the distribution tails. It has been shown that the C₂-based variant of the test requires a smaller number of observations to achieve a predefined statistical power in comparison to the traditional mean-based variant of the test. Depending

on the distribution and its parameters, the significance level, the sample size and the alternative hypothesis, the relative efficiency of the C₂-based test modification over the conventional one-sample t-test varies in a wide range. In the case of symmetric distributions, significance level $\alpha=0.05$ and samples with sizes up to 50 observations, this range is from 40% to 95%.

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